

APPENDIX A - Supplementary material

Table A1 – Key Constructs Used in The Study

Construct	Definition	Sources
Hype translation	Intra-organizational process through which symbolic narratives surrounding AI are interpreted, negotiated, and enacted within specific organizational contexts.	Logue & Grimes, 2022 Czarniawska & Joerges, 1996
Sensemaking	Users' interpretation of AI hype and relevance to daily work.	Weick, 1979, 1995
Sensegiving	Managerial efforts to frame AI hype and influence others' interpretations.	Gioia & Chittipeddi, 1991
AI ambiguity	Ambiguity spanning epistemic (what is AI?), functional (what does it do?), and operational (how to make it work?).	Emerged inductively
Relational coordination	Communication and feedback mechanisms linking managers, users, and vendors.	
Cultural framing	Aligning AI adoption with organizational values, identities, and professional logics	
Symbolic reinforcement	Structural and symbolic signals (mandates, executives' sponsorship, usage rituals) sustaining legitimacy of AI adoption.	

Table A2 – Coding Scheme for Table 2

This table details the coding scheme used to derive the constructs of interpretive tension, translation practices, and implementation outcomes presented in Table 2. These constructs emerged inductively from our data analysis. Through open coding, we identified recurring themes that we consolidated into three core constructs: (1) interpretive tension, reflecting the degree of ambiguity and contested meaning surrounding AI; (2) translation practices, encompassing relational coordination, cultural framing, and symbolic reinforcement; and (3) implementation outcomes, capturing whether projects became transformative, operational, or illusionary. After that, we used axial coding to compare these across cases, focusing on their presence, consistency, and intensity. Finally, we rated each construct as low, medium, or high, based on empirical indicators such as the frequency of cross-functional meetings or the extent of managerial engagement. These ratings enabled us to systematically connect observed practices to the typology of implementation outcomes.

Construct	Definition	Intensity			Empirical indicators	
		Low	Medium	High		
Interpretive Tension	Degree of ambiguity and divergence in how AI hype is perceived internally.	Strong alignment around a shared narrative of AI relevance and purpose.	Partial alignment: some actors share meaning, others diverge.	Strong divergence between managers and practitioners; hype seen as irrelevant or confusing.	Consistency of narratives in interviews between different stakeholders (managers and practitioners); alignment in meeting notes; coherence between vendor point of view and internal talk.	
Translation practices	Relational Coordination (T1)	Practices to involve and connect stakeholders across organizational boundaries.	Minimal interaction; siloed work; limited vendor-user coordination.	Some coordination, but uneven; occasional user input, partial vendor alignment.	Frequent, structured coordination across functions; user voices integrated; strong vendor alignment.	Meeting frequency, co-designing workshops, user engagement in project activities.
	Cultural Framing (T2)	Practices to reframe hype into contextually meaningful opportunities or values.	Hype discussed in abstract, disconnected terms; no attempt to localize.	Partial reframing: hype tied to some organizational goals but remains abstract.	Strong reframing: hype consistently tied to strategic priorities and concrete local needs.	References to organizational identity, long term vision, strategic plans, scaling local use cases.
	Symbolic Reinforcement (T3)	Practices to sustain legitimacy around AI through symbolic cues and institutional scaffolding.	No symbolic enactment: hype treated as routine IT.	Some symbolic reinforcement (pilots, showcase events) but not sustained.	Strong symbolic reinforcement (top-management engagement, success stories, public recognition).	Internal success stories, press releases, awards, pilot showcases, executive sponsorship.
Implementation Outcome	The final result of translating hype: transformative, operational, or illusionary.	Illusionary: symbolic adoption, no real use.	Operational: functional improvements but limited transformative change.	Transformative: technology embedded, reshaping practices and strategy.	Evidence of sustained use, integration into workflows, strategic impact, or abandonment despite hype.	